

Effectiveness of George & Doto's Five-Step Method Compared to Conventional Approach for Teaching Intravenous Injection Skill to Undergraduate Medical Students

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Abstract:

Introduction: In medical education, acquisition of psychomotor skills is critical for patient care, and conventional teaching method (CTM) attains poor acquisition & retention. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate effectiveness of George & Doto's five-step method (FTM) compared to the CTM in teaching intravenous (IV) injection skill to undergraduate medical students.

Methods: It was a double-blinded randomised controlled trial involving 60 students divided into two equal groups using computerised random number table. Control group was taught IV injection skill using CTM by co-investigator while test group was taught using FTM by investigator with student-teacher ratio of 15:1. Pre-validated feedback forms were given to both groups after teaching sessions & responses were collected. Objectively Structured Practical Exam (OSPE) was conducted using pre-validated checklist & timer after one month by independent examiners. Data were collected & analysed with descriptive statistics, chi-square test & Mann-Whitney U-test using Graph pad 10.2.3 (403).

Results: 29 students from each group appeared for OSPE. Statistically significant difference was observed between mean scores of test group (8.5 ± 1.28) & control group (6.1 ± 1.74) ($p < 0.001$, Mann Whitney U-test). Number of students correctly performed most steps were significantly higher in test group compared to control group ($p < 0.05$, χ^2 test). Mean number of students responded, "Strongly agree" in feedback form was 17.9 in test group compared to 12.4 in control group.

Conclusion: FTM found to be more effective than the CTM for teaching IV injection skill, however, further research with larger sample sizes and diverse skills is recommended to validate these findings.

Keywords: George and Doto's five-step method, Conventional teaching method, psychomotor skill, Intravenous injection skill, Undergraduate medical students.

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Introduction

A good doctor-patient relationship requires efficient use of cognitive, psychomotor and affective skills. Proficiency in psychomotor skill directly affects the quality of patient care [1]. Therefore, Competency Based Medical Education (CBME) 2019 rightfully emphasizes acquisition of psychomotor skill [2]. The skills training module for undergraduate medical education 2019 defines Skill as the "Ability to perform a task leading to predefined specific outcome [3].

Intravenous injection is a basic psychomotor skill required at any level of health care. According to CBME 2019, an Indian Medical Graduate (IMG) is expected to administer a drug through an intravenous route independently without any mistake in technique [2]. In a second professional year, a teaching session on the administration of

drugs through various routes is included in the new CBME curriculum of Pharmacology. An Intravenous injection arm (adult) mannequin should be used to teach this skill.

Teaching a psychomotor skill in medical education is a difficult task. While planning such a teaching session, emphasis should be given to the optimal use of time that provides an effective, engaging, and satisfactory learning experience for students [4]. In the conventional teaching approach (CTM), the teacher briefly introduces the theoretical aspect of the skill and then discusses the steps with demonstration. However, there might not be repetition or recall from students. Few articles suggest that CTM lacks well-defined structure resulting in poor acquisition and retention of the skill [1,5]. Apart from teaching, appropriate

feedback during the performance of the skill is a key element in effective skill acquisition in simulation-aided medical education [6]. Additionally, the teaching sessions for psychomotor skill should be based on principles of andragogy and Miller's pyramid of learning psychomotor skill. However, conventional teaching approach does not completely adhere to it [5].

There are various alternative approaches that utilize above-mentioned principles like George & Doto's five-step teaching method (FTM), Peyton's approach etc. The FTM is described below.

1. Overview: Teacher discusses theoretical aspect of the skill including when to and when not to use the skill and information about the instruments needed to perform the skill. At the end of the discussion, students should be motivated to learn the skill.
2. Silent demonstration of the procedure from start to end.
3. Demonstration with details of each step with its importance.
4. Students recall and tell the step to teacher before he/she performs it.
5. Practice by student and spontaneous feedback by teacher.

Very few studies have compared the five-step method with conventional method in medical and paramedical students. Therefore, present study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the FTM vs CTM for teaching intravenous injection on a mannequin in second year MBBS students.

Materials and Methods

It was a double-blinded randomised controlled trial conducted at the Department of Pharmacology, GMERS Medical College, Vadnagar.

A total of sixty undergraduate medical students of second professional year were enrolled in the study through voluntary participation after written informed consent. Students were divided in two groups (n=30), control group and test group, using computerised random number table by their roll numbers. An IV injection Arm (adult) P50/1, made of 3B Skin like silicone was used as mannequin for teaching an intravenous injection skill to both the groups. Other important items like cotton dipped in spirit, tourniquet, sample prescription, vial with label, different sizes of syringes and needles were placed in a tray near the mannequin to perform the skill. The arrangement of items on the table was similar for both the groups. Students of the control group were taught intravenous injection skill on a mannequin using CTM by co-investigator while students of the test group were taught the same skill

using FTM by investigator. Students in either group were unaware of the teaching methodology being used. Two-hour long teaching sessions were carried out on two successive days, with student-teacher ratio of 15:1. At the end of teaching session, students of both the groups were given pre-validated feedback form containing 10 questions that could be answered on a 5-point likert scale i.e. "Strongly agree", "Agree", "Don't know", "Disagree" and "Strongly disagree"(Annexure 1). They were informed about the anonymity of the feedback.

Two independent examiners blinded to groups were assigned to conduct objectively structured practical exam (OSPE) after one month using a pre-validated checklist & a timer. Students were informed one week prior to exam. Pre-validated checklist for IV injection had 13 steps with each step carrying 0.5 to 1.5 marks depending on its relative importance that totals to 10 marks. Students of both the groups were randomly divided between two independent examiners and each student was asked to demonstrate the skill on a mannequin. Arrangement for the demonstration of the skill was similar to the teaching sessions. The examiners were instructed to tick on the steps correctly performed by the students as per checklist. They were also instructed to record the time taken for the demonstration by each student.

Data was entered in Microsoft Excel work sheet, analysed using descriptive statistics, and compared using chi square test and Mann-Whitney U-test. p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Free trial version of Graph pad 10.2.3 (403) was used for analysis.

Results

A total of 60 students participated in the study which were divided equally into test group (n=30) and control group (n=30) by randomization. Out of 60 students, a total of 58 students appeared for the OPSE. One student from each group was absent. Male to female ratio in test group was 1.6:1 compared to 0.93:1 in control group. The difference in male to female ratio between test group and control group was not statistically significant (p=0.29, χ^2 test). Maximum score for correctly performed skill was 10. Mean score of test group was 8.5±1.28 compared to control group which was 6.1±1.74 (Figure 1). Difference in the mean scores between test group and control group was statistically significant when Mann Whitney U-test was applied (p < 0.001). Median score of test group was 8.7, higher than the median score of control group that was 6.2.

Figure 1: Comparison of mean scores in test & control group

Mean time required to perform the skill was 1.90 ± 0.68 and 1.37 ± 0.44 minutes respectively for test & control group. Statistically significant difference was observed between test group and control group in the number of students correctly performed the step 1, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13 ($p < 0.05$, χ^2 test) of IV injection skill (Table 1).

Table 1: Number of students correctly performed each step of intravenous injection in control & test group

No.	Step	Control (N=29) (%)	Test (N=29) (%)	p Value
1	Check the prescription orders and ampoule/vial for medication name, dose & expiry date	6(20.7)	24(82.7)	<0.00001*
2	Apply tourniquet	20(69)	26(89.6)	0.052
3	Wash hands and allow hands to dry – Apply disposable gloves	9(31)	12(41.4)	0.412
4	Sterilize site by spirit swab (Centre to periphery – 20 sec)	19 (65.5)	26(89.6)	0.027*
5	a. A. Place needle on syringe without touching their tip &	28 (96.6)	28 (96.6)	1
	b. Suck as much air into syringe as the volume of solution to be injected	27 (93.1)	25 (86.2)	0.388
6	a. Insert needle on the top of vial	28 (96.6)	28 (96.6)	1
	b. Turn it upside down	28 (96.6)	28 (96.6)	1
	c. Pump air into vial	22 (75.9)	27 (93.1)	0.069
	d. Withdraw prescribed amount of drug	22 (75.9)	27 (93.1)	0.069
	d. Remove air bubble if any	17 (58.6)	23 (79.3)	0.088
7	Pull the skin in longitudinal direction of vein	10 (34.5)	18 (62.1)	0.035*
8	Insert needle with bevel up at angle of 25-35 degree	23 (79.3)	28 (96.6)	0.044*
9	Slowly aspirate blood to confirm	18 (62.1)	25 (86.2)	0.036*
10	Loosen the tourniquet	9 (31)	19 (65.5)	0.008*
11	Slowly inject the drug (1ml/10sec) and slowly remove the needle	21 (72.4)	29 (100)	0.002*
12	Secure puncture site with adhesive tape	15 (51.7)	23 (79.3)	0.027*
13	Disposal of needle, syringe & vial	3 (10.3)	16 (55.2)	0.0002*

*Statistically significant difference in number of students correctly performed the step between test group and control group (χ^2 test, $p < 0.05$)

Feedback of students between FTM&CTM was collected using five-point likert scale. Mean number of students responded, “Strongly agree” to all 10 questions was 17.9 in test group whereas it was 12.4 in control group. Students in test group

responded with “strongly agree” or “agree” for all questions except question no. 6 that was about student’s ability to predict time taken to perform the skill, in which, four students responded with “Don’t know”.

In contrast, many students of control group have responded with “Don’t know” (n=17), “Disagree” (n=6) and “Strongly disagree” (n=2). Out of 29 students in test group, 80% of students were strongly agreed that they feel motivated to learn the skill after discussion of theoretical aspect, the silent

demonstration of a skill by teacher helped 67 % of students in their performance, 73% students were actively involved in learning and the learning experience was enjoyable for 73% of students (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Feedback of students regarding used teaching methodology on five-point likert scale (n=30 in control & test group each)

Note: Refer Annexure 1 for feedback questionnaire.

Annexure 1: Five-point Likert Scale(Rate your score regarding the teaching session on Intravenous injection skill)

1.	I completely understood the theoretical aspect of giving intravenous injection.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
2.	I was motivated to learn the skill after the theoretical aspect.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
3.	The silent demonstration of a teacher helped me in performing the skill better.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
4.	Description of each step helped me to better understand & memorize the skill.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
5.	I am able to recall the sequence of steps.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
6.	I am able to predict the time taken to perform the skill.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
7.	I was actively involved in learning the skill.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
8.	I got immediate feedback during performance of the skill.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
9.	I feel more confident to perform the skill.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	
10.	It was an enjoyable learning experience for me.				
Strongly agree	Agree	Don't know	Disagree	Strongly disagree	

Discussion

Mastery of a health care professional over psychomotor/ procedural skill is an important determinant

of qualitative patient care and therefore, teaching a psychomotor skill is an integral part of medical education. However, conventional teaching method

attains poor acquisition and retention. The FTM is based on principles of andragogy and taxonomy of psychomotor domain. Present study compared effectiveness of the FTM and CTM for teaching intravenous injection skill on a mannequin.

The results suggest that the FTM is more effective than CTM for teaching intravenous injection skill on a mannequin in second year medical students. Feedback from students also showed that it is more effective, engaging and enjoyable learning method than conventional approach.

In present study, the mean score of test group & control group was 8.5 ± 1.28 and 6.1 ± 1.74 (out of 10) respectively which was statistically significant. A study conducted by Paralikar et al. (2022) found similar results for per abdomen and respiratory examination skills in 3rd sem MBBS students ($n=58$) [8]. The mean scores of test and control group were 57 ± 2 & 45 ± 6 (out of 60) for the six abdominal skills and 34 ± 4.5 & 25 ± 10.5 (out of 40) for the four respiratory skills. Another study done by Jin Young Kim showed that the FTM has significantly increased performance ability of nursing students in infant cardiopulmonary resuscitation on a mannequin [9]. These findings suggest that retention and recall rate is high when students are taught the psychomotor skill using the FTM. This is probably due to amalgamation of various learning theories in this method which solidifies the memory of a learnt skill. Median score of test & control group was 8.7 and 6.2 respectively in our study. Paralikar et al (2022) also found significantly higher median scores in six per abdomen and three respiratory examination skills.

Analysis of individual steps showed that a higher number of students have correctly performed steps of IV injection in test group as compared to control group. The difference was statistically significant for majority of steps (9 out of 13). These were very critical steps for accurate administration of IV injection. E.g. Checking the prescription & vial/ampoule for dose, expiry date ensures that right patient receives right medicine in accurate dose, sterilization of injection site is also very important that checks the entry of pathogen into blood stream. This finding illustrates value of structured teaching methodology that emphasizes critical procedural elements. Time required to perform the skill was higher in test group (1.90 ± 0.68 minutes) compared to control group (1.37 ± 0.44 minutes) in our study. Paralikar et al haven't recorded time needed for procedure in their study. A study by Rossettini et al. (2017) using Peyton's approach showed that the time needed to perform the procedure i.e. C1-C2 passive right rotation was considerably short for intervention group immediately, one week & one month after teaching session in physiotherapy students ($n=39$) [10]. On the contrary, Orde et al. (2010) using Peyton's approach found no significant

difference in time required to perform the skill i.e. laryngeal mask insertion on a mannequin in final year medical students ($n=120$) [11]. Generally, after repeated practice & acquisition of skill, a student requires less time to perform the skill. The possible reason for our finding is that students in control group did not able to recall all the steps so they required less time for performing less number of steps while the test group took slightly longer because they might be prioritizing accuracy and thoroughness, indicative of a deeper understanding of the skill. Another study published by Viridi & Sood (2011) showed effectiveness of five-step method in fissure sealant placement skill in undergraduate dental students [12]. The sealant retention rate was 92% at 6 & 12 months and 90% at 18 months of the procedure.

The students' feedback further supports the positive impact of the FTM. Notably, a large majority of students in the test group reported feeling motivated to learn and actively engaged in the learning process. This is consistent with the theory of social cognition, which states that setting clear goals and active engagement in educational activities improve motivation and self-efficacy [13]. Paralikar et al. (2022) also found high acceptance rating for George & Doto's method for learning clinical skills. A study conducted by Piryani et al. (2013) also found high feedback score for five-step method in physiotherapy students [14].

Conclusion

The present study shows that the FTM is more effective for teaching psychomotor skill in Pharmacology compared to the CTM.

The strength of the study lies in its methodology. Randomization was performed during group allocation that ensured better allocation of high & under-achievers in both groups. This improves the validity of the study. Students were blinded to the teaching methodology used and examiners were blinded to the groups, which helped to prevent bias. To the best of our knowledge, this is also the second-only study to evaluate effectiveness of the FTM in medical students. However, there are few limitations like high student-teacher ratio. A systematic review on effectiveness of Peyton's approach suggest that it is most effective with student teacher ratio of 1:1 [15]. In our study, it was 15:1. An ideal student teacher ratio is difficult to achieve with less faculty and large number of students. Additionally, many studies have showed effectiveness of Peyton's approach with student teacher ratio as high as 13:1[15]. A small sample size is also one of the limitations of the study.

We can recommend that George & Doto's method can be used as an alternative approach to teach psychomotor skill in Pharmacology.

Further studies are recommended to evaluate this method for other psychomotor skills in different medical subjects with large sample size.

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